

On Universality and Efficient Arithmetic Realisation of Ternary Logic Gates

Rhiddhi Prasad Das
School of Computer Engineering
KIIT Deemed to be University
Bhubaneswar, India
Email: rhiddhiprasad@gmail.com

Jyotiprakash Mishra
School of Computer Engineering
KIIT Deemed to be University
Bhubaneswar, India
Email: jyotiprakash.mishrafcs@kiit.ac.in

Abstract—What if the transistor had been built to count to two, not because it was optimal, but because it was convenient? The field of binary (base-2) logic has overshadowed a plethora of alternative possibilities in computing since the 1950s, and certain types of hardware or logical systems may be better suited for specific tasks, a question that is especially relevant in the development of intelligent systems or simulator frameworks. Ternary (base-3) logic is explored as a relatively overlooked yet promising alternative, with potential advantages in information density, circuit depth, and alignment with emerging multi-valued hardware, and its capacity for universality as well as its performance in arithmetic operations as compared to binary systems is examined. All 19,683 binary-arity ternary gates are systematically evaluated, confirming that exactly 3,774 are functionally complete, consistent with Martin’s 1954 result, and the search is optimised via Clone Theory and Group Theory, classifying these gates into 322 equivalence classes under the $S_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$ symmetry group and yielding a $47,105.7\times$ search speedup. A key theoretical contribution establishes that unary completeness of a binary-arity gate implies full functional completeness via Rosenberg’s theorem, reducing the universality test from 19,683 binary functions to just 27 unary functions, a speed-up that is $10,529\times$ faster than the naive approach. Structural analysis reveals that all universal gates are surjective, none are self-dual or zero-preserving, and only 2.4% are commutative. Depth-optimal and size-optimal synthesis algorithms are applied across all 322 class representatives to construct balanced ternary half-adder and full-adder circuits, assessed in terms of gate count, logical depth, and propagation delay against known optimal binary designs. The best-performing gate achieves a half-adder sum depth of 3 and carry depth of 4, yielding a full-adder carry depth of 10 with 29 gates, compared to depth 8 and 21 gates for the binary NAND full adder. Crucially, the information-density advantage of ternary ($\log_2 3 \approx 1.585$ bits per trit) means that at 32 bits, the ternary ripple-carry adder achieves 18% lower propagation depth and 9.4% fewer gates than its binary counterpart, with advantages increasing at wider data paths. Potential implications for emerging computing paradigms, including AI/ML hardware, neuromorphic systems, and analog in-memory computing, are discussed, and a structured framework for evaluating ternary logic in next-generation computational architectures is provided.

Index Terms—Ternary Logic, Universal Gate, Full Adder, Functional Completeness, Clone Theory

I. INTRODUCTION

Binary logic has dominated the design of digital systems for decades, owing to its simplicity, robustness, and compatibility with existing hardware. However, this dominance

does not imply optimality across all computational paradigms. As emerging fields such as neuromorphic and analog-inspired computing gain traction, it becomes increasingly relevant to explore alternative logical systems that may offer improved expressiveness or efficiency.

Among these, ternary logic (base-3) presents a compelling direction. By extending the discrete state space beyond binary, ternary systems have the potential to reduce circuit depth, encode richer information per signal, and better align with certain physical substrates.

A fundamental question in the study of any logical system is that of *universality*, whether a given set of gates can be composed to realise all possible functions within the logic. Establishing universality is essential, as it determines the completeness and practical viability of a logic family for general-purpose computation.

Beyond theoretical completeness, the practical realisation of arithmetic circuits in ternary logic is equally critical. Efficient implementations of components such as adders provide insight into trade-offs in gate count, latency, and structural complexity, serving as a benchmark for comparing ternary systems against their binary counterparts.

In this work, a comprehensive analysis of ternary logic gates is conducted with respect to both universality and arithmetic efficiency. A large space of candidate gates is systematically explored, and subsets exhibiting desirable functional completeness and implementation efficiency are identified. These gates are further evaluated through their application in ternary arithmetic circuit design.

The contributions of this paper are as follows:

- A group-theoretic framework for identifying universal ternary logic gates through isomorphic class reduction.
- A composition-based algorithm for constructing arbitrary truth tables via repeated application of a given seed gate.
- A unification of unary and binary functional completeness under a common formulation.
- Systematic evaluation of ternary arithmetic realisations, with emphasis on full adders, in terms of gate count, depth and latency.
- Comparative efficiency analysis between ternary and binary logic architectures.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews prior work in multi-valued logic systems. Section III introduces the necessary background on ternary logic and functional completeness. Section IV presents the proposed framework for universality analysis. Section V details the gate composition framework and search space optimisation. Section VI presents the arithmetic realisations and their evaluation. Section VII reports experimental results and comparative analysis. Finally, Section VIII concludes the paper and outlines future directions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature surrounding ternary logic spans theoretical foundations, circuit-level design, and emerging hardware motivations. This section surveys prior work across four areas directly relevant to the contributions of this paper, identifying the gap that the present work addresses.

A. Multi-Valued Logic and Functional Completeness

Multi-valued logic extends classical binary logic by allowing variables to assume more than two discrete values, with ternary logic being one of the most studied cases. Early foundational work by Łukasiewicz [1] introduced formal systems of three-valued logic, establishing a basis for reasoning beyond binary domains, which was later complemented by Kleene's formulation [2] of three-valued logic with an emphasis on partial truth and indeterminacy.

The notion of functional completeness, central to this study, was rigorously characterised in Boolean systems by Post [3] through the development of Post's lattice [4], which classifies all Boolean function classes based on closure properties. This concept serves as a direct motivation for investigating completeness in higher-valued systems. In parallel, Shannon's work on switching theory [5], [6] provided the practical and theoretical foundations for realising logical functions using physical circuits, reinforcing the importance of universal gate sets.

Extending these ideas to multi-valued logic introduces significant structural complexity, which is effectively addressed through clone theory as developed by Rosenberg [7]. Clone theory provides a systematic framework for analysing sets of functions under composition and identifying conditions for functional completeness in multi-valued domains. This framework is particularly relevant to the present study, where the universality of ternary logic gates is examined through compositional and closure-based analysis.

B. Ternary Arithmetic Circuit Design

Ternary arithmetic circuit design extends conventional binary arithmetic by operating over a three-valued domain, typically represented as $\{-1, 0, 1\}$ in balanced ternary systems or $\{0, 1, 2\}$ in unbalanced systems. Among these, the balanced ternary representation is often preferred due to its symmetry around zero, which can simplify carry propagation and overall arithmetic operations [8]. This advantage serves as the primary reason for its adoption in this paper.

Fundamental building blocks of ternary arithmetic include the ternary half adder and full adder, which compute sum and carry values for inputs drawn from a three-valued set [9]. While ternary systems introduce a larger input space compared to binary, the structure of balanced ternary allows carry and sum behaviour to remain well-defined and systematic, avoiding excessive complexity in practical implementations [10].

Prior work in this area has explored various implementations of ternary adders using different logic formulations and hardware paradigms [11]. These designs often focus on minimising gate count, reducing propagation delay, or optimising carry generation mechanisms, with several approaches demonstrating that efficient realisations are achievable despite the higher radix [12].

In the context of this study, ternary arithmetic circuits serve as a practical benchmark for evaluating the effectiveness of functionally complete gate sets. The ability of a gate or set of gates to efficiently realise ternary adders provides insight into its suitability for real-world computational applications.

C. Emerging Hardware Motivations

Interest in multi-valued logic systems is not purely theoretical, but is also motivated by potential advantages in hardware design. By increasing the radix of computation, multi-valued systems such as ternary logic can reduce the number of interconnections and logic depth required to represent and process information, which is particularly relevant in modern scaling-limited architectures [13].

One of the earliest practical demonstrations of ternary computing was the *Setun* computer, developed in the Soviet Union in 1958, with a later improved version known as *Setun-70* [14]. These systems operated using balanced ternary representation and demonstrated that non-binary computation could be both feasible and efficient in hardware. Notably, the use of balanced ternary enabled simpler arithmetic operations and reduced hardware redundancy compared to equivalent binary implementations [8].

In contemporary research, emerging device technologies such as memristors, resistive RAM (RRAM), and other non-volatile memory elements have renewed interest in multi-valued logic [15]. These devices naturally support multiple stable states, making them well-suited for implementing ternary and higher-radix logic directly at the hardware level [16]. Such properties open pathways toward in-memory computing, neuromorphic systems, and energy-efficient architectures [17].

Within this context, the study of functional completeness and efficient gate realisations in ternary logic becomes increasingly relevant. Identifying compact and universal gate sets is essential for leveraging the advantages of multi-valued hardware, particularly in systems where area, power, and latency are critical constraints [11].

D. Research Gap

While prior work has established the total number of functionally complete ternary gates, i.e. 3,774, first shown by

Martin [18] all the way back in 1954, there is limited exploration of their practical utility in constructing specific target functions. In particular, existing research does not explicitly analyze how these universal gates perform when synthesizing concrete logic structures.

This paper addresses this gap by systematically evaluating each universal ternary gate based on its ability to generate a target truth table, specifically the ternary sum and carry functions. Furthermore, it investigates the relative suitability of these gates for different design objectives.

Finally, the resulting implementations are compared against conventional binary architectures in terms of circuit size, latency, and carry propagation characteristics, providing a practical perspective on the advantages and trade-offs of ternary logic systems.

III. BACKGROUND AND PRELIMINARIES

Before getting started with the contributions of this study, an overview of all the concepts used, implemented, or connected seems necessary and will underpin a smoother read. These topics involve the basics of ternary logic systems, their representation as balanced ternary, and a quick dive into functional completeness and clone theory, so that, ahead in the paper, the proofs or algorithms become easier to grasp.

A. Ternary Logic Systems

Ternary logic systems extend classical binary logic by allowing variables to take values from a three-element set, typically denoted as $T = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ or $\{0, 1, 2\}$. A ternary logic function of arity n is defined as $f : T^n \rightarrow T$, resulting in a significantly larger function space compared to binary logic. For instance, while there are 2^{2^n} Boolean functions of n variables, the number of ternary functions grows as 3^{3^n} , highlighting the increased expressive capacity of multi-valued systems.

Ternary logic has been studied in various forms, including systems proposed by Łukasiewicz [1] and Kleene [2], each differing in their interpretation of intermediate truth values. In the context of this work, the focus lies not on logical interpretation, but on the structural and computational properties of ternary functions, particularly their ability to form functionally complete sets.

An important aspect of ternary logic is the distinction between the domain of values and the arity of functions. A function may be ternary-valued while having unary, binary, or higher arity, a distinction that becomes critical when analysing universality and functional completeness in multi-valued systems.

B. Balanced Ternary Representation

Balanced ternary is a representation of ternary logic in which the digit set is defined as $\{-, 0, +\}$, providing symmetry around zero. This contrasts with the unbalanced representation $\{0, 1, 2\}$, where such symmetry is absent. The balanced form offers several advantages in arithmetic and circuit design,

particularly in simplifying carry propagation and enabling more uniform treatment of positive and negative values.

In balanced ternary arithmetic, addition naturally incorporates negative contributions, often reducing the need for separate subtraction operations. This symmetry leads to more structured and predictable behaviour in arithmetic circuits, making it a suitable choice for analysing ternary logic gates in a computational setting.

To illustrate common logical operations in this domain, several ternary analogues of classical Boolean gates can be defined. Let $x, y \in \{-, 0, +\}$. The following operator conventions are used:

$$\tilde{x} = -x, \quad x \wedge y = \min(x, y), \quad x \vee y = \max(x, y) \quad (1)$$

NOT:

$$\text{NOT}(x) = \tilde{x} \quad \begin{array}{c} \left[\begin{array}{c} - \\ 0 \\ + \end{array} \right] \xrightarrow{\text{NOT}} \left[\begin{array}{c} + \\ 0 \\ - \end{array} \right] \end{array} \quad (2)$$

AND: $\text{AND}(x, y) = x \wedge y$

	-	0	+
-	-	-	-
0	-	0	0
+	-	0	+

OR: $\text{OR}(x, y) = x \vee y$

	-	0	+
-	-	0	+
0	0	0	+
+	+	+	+

NAND: $\text{NAND}(x, y) = \widetilde{x \wedge y}$

	-	0	+
-	+	+	+
0	+	0	0
+	+	0	-

XOR: $\text{XOR}(x, y) = (\tilde{x} \wedge y) \vee (y \wedge \tilde{x})$

	-	0	+
-	-	0	+
0	0	0	0
+	+	0	-

These examples demonstrate how classical logical operations can be extended into the balanced ternary domain using order-based operators and negation. For this study, all ternary functions and truth tables are expressed using the balanced ternary domain, providing a consistent framework for analysing composition and functional completeness.

C. Functional Completeness and Clone Theory

Functional completeness is a central concept in logic design, referring to the ability of a set of operations to express all possible functions over a given domain through composition. In the binary setting, this notion is well understood through results such as Post's lattice, which classifies all Boolean

function classes based on closure properties and identifies complete sets such as NAND and NOR.

Extending this idea to ternary logic significantly increases the size and structural complexity of the function space. For a domain $T = \{-, 0, +\}$, an n -ary function is defined as $f : T^n \rightarrow T$, and the total number of such functions grows as 3^{3^n} . As a result, determining whether a given function or set of functions is complete becomes a non-trivial problem.

Clone theory provides a formal framework for analysing such questions. A *clone* is defined as a set of functions that is closed under composition and contains all projection functions. Functional completeness can then be characterised as the ability of a function set to generate the *full clone*, i.e., the set of all possible functions over the domain.

A key result in this context is due to Rosenberg, who showed that for finite domains, any clone that contains all unary functions and at least one non-projection function must be the full clone. This result establishes a powerful bridge between unary completeness and full functional completeness, implying that the ability to generate all unary functions is, under mild conditions, sufficient to guarantee universality [7].

In multi-valued logic, clone structures are far richer than in the Boolean case, and no simple lattice analogous to Post's classification exists in general. Instead, completeness must often be established through structural properties such as preservation of relations, monotonicity, or invariance under specific transformations.

In the context of this study, clone-theoretic ideas are used to analyse the expressive power of ternary logic gates under composition. In particular, the relationship between unary completeness and full completeness, as characterised by Rosenberg's result, provides a theoretical foundation for evaluating whether a given ternary gate can generate all required functions.

IV. UNIVERSALITY IN TERNARY LOGIC

Coming from binary logic systems, one may presume that the NAND gate, as in binary logic, would be universal in ternary as well; at least, this was the initial thought process at the beginning of this research. The fact is that it is not: the NAND gate is not only incomplete in binary arity (2-input gates), but it was found that it is also not complete in unary arity (1-input gates).

To set up some vocabulary for this study and remove confusion up ahead, this paper will refer to:

- Base-2 logic gates \implies Binary Logic Gates
- Base-3 logic gates \implies Ternary Logic Gates
- Base- N logic gates \implies N -ary Logic Gates
- 1 input logic gates \implies Unary-arity Logic Gates
- 2 input logic gates \implies Binary-arity Logic Gates
- N input logic gates \implies N -ary arity Logic Gates

So if a logic gate has 2 inputs and is defined over 3-valued logic, this study will refer to it as a Binary-arity Ternary Gate (BT-Gate). Similarly, a 1-input gate over the binary logic domain will be called a Unary-arity Binary Gate (UB-Gate).

This section will analyse and discuss methods, algorithms and theorems to search for actual universal binary-arity ternary gates that can solely generate all ternary logic gates.

A. Unary Completeness

A gate is said to be *unary complete* if it can generate all possible 1-input, 1-output functions through composition. Drawing an analogy from Boolean logic, such a gate must be capable of producing all possible mappings from the set $\{0, 1\}$ to itself. These mappings correspond to all possible assignments of outputs to the inputs, as illustrated in (2).

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

As for a formal definition, it is provided as follows:

Definition 1. Let T be a finite set with $|T| = n \geq 2$, and let $g : T^k \rightarrow T$ be a k -ary function. The gate g is said to be **unary complete** if the clone generated by g , denoted $\text{Clone}(g)$, contains every unary function $f : T \rightarrow T$.

Hence, in ternary logic, a gate is said to be unary complete if it can generate all $3^3 = 27$ unary functions over the domain $T = \{-, 0, +\}$. These functions can be categorised based on their structural properties as follows:

- **Constant functions** (Count: 3): functions that map every input to a fixed value in T .

$$\begin{bmatrix} - \\ 0 \\ + \end{bmatrix} \xrightarrow{C_0} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

- **Bijective functions** (Count: 6): permutations of the set T , corresponding to all invertible mappings. This would include Buffer, Not, Increment and Decrement functions.

$$\begin{bmatrix} - \\ 0 \\ + \end{bmatrix} \xrightarrow{Inc} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ + \\ - \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

- **Delta (indicator) functions** (Count: 3): functions that isolate a single input value, typically mapping one element of T to $+$ while mapping the others to $-$.

$$\begin{bmatrix} - \\ 0 \\ + \end{bmatrix} \xrightarrow{\delta_-} \begin{bmatrix} + \\ - \\ - \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

- **Non-bijective, non-constant functions** (Count: 15): all remaining mappings that neither preserve distinctness of inputs nor collapse entirely to a constant.

Together, these classes exhaust the space of unary functions on T , and the ability of a gate to generate all such mappings through composition is a necessary condition for unary completeness.

B. Binary Completeness

A gate is considered to be *binary complete* if it can generate all k^{k^2} 2-input 1-output gates in base- k logic. As far as the analogy of Boolean algebra and binary logic is concerned, the NAND and NOR gate are the only 2 gates that are binary complete in base-2, given they can generate all the Boolean functions possible through composition.

Definition 2. Let T be a finite set with $|T| = n \geq 2$, and let $g : T^k \rightarrow T$ be a k -ary function. The gate g is said to be **binary complete** if the clone generated by g , denoted $\text{Clone}(g)$, contains every binary function $f : T^2 \rightarrow T$.

The total number of binary-arity binary gates present are $2^{2^2} = 16$ which is easily traceable by hand but as we move on to ternary, this number explodes exponentially as the total number of binary-arity ternary gates are $3^{3^2} = 19,683$ making it really hard and rigorous to search this space by hand.

By Shannon's switch and relay theory [5], the ability to construct a basic selector circuit suffices to realise any possible logic gate in the domain. Hence, if we have access to constants, Not, and Delta from unary completeness, along with the OR gate and the AND gate, we can form any logic gate possible. This requirement can be further reduced in complexity: if a gate can generate the necessary unary functions and a single NAND-like gate in k -ary logic, then that NAND-like gate can be used to generate AND and OR gates, and we can technically create any logical gate possible.

An algorithm that can detect whether the necessary unary-arity functions were generated can filter out candidate gates for universality, as a gate that is not unary complete cannot be binary complete. This statement is formally presented as a lemma and proved as follows.

Lemma 1. If a gate is binary complete, then it is unary complete.

Proof. Let $U : T \rightarrow T$ be any unary function. Define a binary function $B : T^2 \rightarrow T$ as

$$B(x, y) = U(x) \quad (7)$$

If the gate is binary complete, then all such binary functions B can be generated. Fixing the second argument to a constant $c \in T$, we obtain

$$B(x, c) = U(x) \quad (8)$$

Hence, U can be realised. Since U was arbitrary, all unary functions can be generated, implying unary completeness. \square

Remark 1. For any unary function $U : T \rightarrow T$, define $B(x, y) = U(x)$. If g is binary complete, then $B \in \text{Clone}(g)$, and fixing $y = c$ yields $U(x) = B(x, c)$. Hence, $\forall U, U \in \text{Clone}(g)$, implying unary completeness.

C. Unary Completeness Implies Binary Completeness

During the execution of the composition-based search algorithm, it was empirically observed that the set of unary complete gates coincided exactly with the set of binary complete gates in ternary logic. A similar correspondence is also seen in binary logic, where the only unary complete gates (NAND and NOR) are also functionally complete.

To explain this phenomenon, we recall a fundamental result from clone theory.

Theorem 2 (Rosenberg, 1970). Let C be a clone on a finite set T with $|T| \geq 2$. If C contains all unary functions and at least one non-projection, then C is the full clone.

Theorem 3. Let $g : T^2 \rightarrow T$ be a gate on a finite set T with $|T| \geq 2$. If g is unary complete, then it is fully complete.

Proof. Let $C = \text{Clone}(g)$. By unary completeness, C contains all unary functions.

It remains to show that g is not a projection. Suppose for contradiction that $g = \pi_i^k$ for some i . Then every composition of g yields only projections, so C contains only projections. However, constant functions are not projections (as they are not surjective when $|T| \geq 2$), contradicting unary completeness. Hence, g is not a projection.

By Theorem 1, C is the full clone, and therefore g is fully complete. \square

Corollary 4. If a gate is unary complete, then it is binary complete.

Proof. Since full completeness implies the ability to generate all functions of every arity, all binary functions $f : T^2 \rightarrow T$ belong to $\text{Clone}(g)$. Hence, g is binary complete. \square

Remark 2. This result provides a theoretical explanation for the empirical observation that unary complete and binary complete gates coincide in ternary logic. It further implies that testing for unary completeness alone suffices to identify universal gates, significantly reducing the computational search space.

V. GATE COMPOSITION FRAMEWORK

To evaluate the expressive power of ternary logic gates, a systematic composition framework is proposed. Given a candidate gate $g : T^2 \rightarrow T$, where $T = \{-, 0, +\}$, the objective is to determine whether a target function, represented using a truth matrix, can be generated through repeated composition of g with itself and with projection functions.

The framework is used to analyse functional completeness by evaluating the generated set against the target functions defined in Sections IV-A and IV-B. The final count is calculated through iterative composition over the target set (or a reduced subset), with search space optimisation achieved by identifying isomorphic gates.

A. Composition Algorithm

The composition process begins with a base set \mathcal{S} consisting of the arbitrary gate Arb and all projection functions. At each iteration, new functions are generated by composing previously obtained functions. For functions $f_1, f_2 \in \mathcal{S}$, a new function h is constructed as:

$$h(x, y) = Arb(f_1(x, y), f_2(x, y)) \quad (9)$$

If h generates a new truth table that has not existed before, or has generated a more efficient formulation for a truth table, it is appended or replaced in the set, respectively. This process is repeated iteratively, expanding the function set until no new functions are produced, indicating closure under composition.

The algorithm to search for all unary complete gates in ternary logic goes through each of the 19,683 gates and checks for the return value of Algorithm 1 to be $3^3 = 27$. The resulting number came out to be 3,774.

Algorithm 1 Composition-Based Search for Unary Gates

Require: Gate $Arb : T^2 \rightarrow T$, search set \mathcal{L}

Ensure: Set of realised target gates

```

1: Initialise  $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2:  $Arb(x) = \{\text{return } Arb(x, x)\}$ 
3:  $\pi_1 = x$ 
4:  $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \mathcal{S} \cup \{Arb(x), \pi_1\}$ 
5: found_set  $\leftarrow \emptyset$ 
6: for all  $v \in \mathcal{S}$  do
7:   if  $v \in \mathcal{L}$  then
8:     found_set  $\leftarrow$  found_set  $\cup \{v\}$ 
9:   end if
10: end for
11: changed  $\leftarrow$  true
12: while changed do
13:   changed  $\leftarrow$  false
14:   current  $\leftarrow$  snapshot of  $\mathcal{S}$ 
15:   for all  $f \in$  current do
16:     for all  $g \in$  current do
17:       Construct  $h$  such that  $h[i] = Arb(f[i], g[i])$  for all
          $i$ 
18:       if  $h \in \mathcal{L}$  then
19:         found_set  $\leftarrow$  found_set  $\cup \{h\}$ 
20:       end if
21:       if  $h \notin \mathcal{S}$  then
22:          $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \mathcal{S} \cup \{h\}$ 
23:         changed  $\leftarrow$  true
24:       end if
25:     end for
26:   end for
27: end while
28: return found_set

```

B. Circuit Analysis Algorithms

The Depth-Optimal Circuit Search (Algorithm V-B) proceeds as a breadth-first expansion over composition depth, operating under a *tree model* in which every gate application is

Algorithm 2 Composition-Based Binary-arity Circuit Search

Require: Gate $Arb : T^2 \rightarrow T$, target function τ

Require: $OptimizeFor \in \{\text{SIZE, DEPTH}\}$

Ensure: Minimum composition depth d to realise τ , or -1 if unrealisable

```

1: Initialise  $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \emptyset$  {Map: truth table  $\rightarrow$  {gate_count,
  depth}}
2:  $\pi_1 = Arb(x, y) : \text{return } x$ 
3:  $\pi_2 = Arb(x, y) : \text{return } y$ 
4:  $\mathcal{S}[\pi_1] \leftarrow \{0, 0\}$ ;  $\mathcal{S}[\pi_2] \leftarrow \{0, 0\}$ ;  $\mathcal{S}[Arb] \leftarrow \{1, 1\}$ 
5: for all  $(f, d_f) \in \mathcal{S}$  do
6:   if  $f = \tau$  then
7:     return  $d_f$ 
8:   end if
9: end for
10: changed  $\leftarrow$  true
11: while changed do
12:   changed  $\leftarrow$  false
13:   current  $\leftarrow$  snapshot of  $\mathcal{S}$ 
14:   for all  $(f, d_f) \in$  current do
15:     for all  $(h, d_h) \in$  current do
16:        $\varphi \leftarrow Arb(f(\cdot), h(\cdot))$  {functional composition}
17:        $gc_\varphi \leftarrow gc_f + gc_h + 1$ 
18:        $dp_\varphi \leftarrow \max(dp_f, dp_h) + 1$ 
19:       if  $\varphi \notin \mathcal{S}$  then
20:          $\mathcal{S}[\varphi] \leftarrow \{gc_\varphi, dp_\varphi\}$ ; changed  $\leftarrow$  true
21:         if  $\varphi = \tau$  then
22:           return  $\mathcal{S}[\varphi]$ 
23:         end if
24:         else if  $OptimizeFor = \text{SIZE}$  then
25:           if  $gc_\varphi < \mathcal{S}[\varphi].gc$  or  $(gc_\varphi = \mathcal{S}[\varphi].gc$  and
              $dp_\varphi < \mathcal{S}[\varphi].dp)$  then
26:              $\mathcal{S}[\varphi] \leftarrow \{gc_\varphi, dp_\varphi\}$ ; changed  $\leftarrow$  true
27:           end if
28:         else if  $OptimizeFor = \text{DEPTH}$  then
29:           if  $dp_\varphi < \mathcal{S}[\varphi].dp$  or  $(dp_\varphi = \mathcal{S}[\varphi].dp$  and
              $gc_\varphi < \mathcal{S}[\varphi].gc)$  then
30:              $\mathcal{S}[\varphi] \leftarrow \{gc_\varphi, dp_\varphi\}$ ; changed  $\leftarrow$  true
31:           end if
32:         end if
33:       end for
34:     end for
35: end while
36: return  $-1$ 

```

counted independently, even if the same subfunction appears in multiple branches. The search is initialised with the two projection functions $\pi_1(x, y) = x$ and $\pi_2(x, y) = y$ at depth zero, maintained in two structures: *all_tts*, the cumulative set of all reachable truth tables, and *prev*, the frontier of truth tables first reached at the previous depth layer. At each depth d , candidate compositions are formed by pairing every element of *all_tts* with every element of *prev* (and symmetrically), ensuring that at least one operand belongs to the current

frontier, a standard BFS condition that prevents re-exploring compositions already covered at shallower depths. For each candidate $h = Arb(f(\cdot), g(\cdot))$, the gate count is accumulated as $gc_h = gc_f + gc_g + 1$, reflecting the tree model assumption that no sharing occurs. Since multiple compositions at the same depth may produce the same truth table with differing gate counts, a per-layer *best_gc* map is maintained and updated greedily. A truth table is admitted to \mathcal{S} only if it is seen for the first time, pinning its depth to d ; if it was already admitted at depth d in a prior iteration of the same layer, its recorded gate count may still be improved. Upon completing a layer, if the target τ was encountered, the algorithm returns the best (gc, d) pair found for τ within that layer, guaranteeing depth optimality. If the frontier *prev* becomes empty, meaning no new truth tables were generated, the search terminates and returns $(-1, -1)$, indicating that τ is unrealisable under the given gate.

The Size-Optimal Circuit Search (Algorithm V-B) reframes the problem as a dynamic programming enumeration over gate count, operating under a *DAG model* in which a synthesised subfunction, once computed, may be reused freely at zero additional cost. Truth tables are grouped by their minimum known gate count in the map *by_size*, initialised with the two projections at size zero. At each size s , new truth tables are generated by composing every pair (f, g) where f has size s_f and g has size $s_g = s - 1 - s_f$, ranging over all valid partitions of $s - 1$ between the two operands; the subtracted unit accounts for the single gate application that combines them. Because the DAG model permits sharing, a truth table once discovered at size s is guaranteed to be size-optimal and is never revisited: the algorithm admits h to *known* only on its first occurrence and immediately returns if $h = \tau$, short-circuiting the search at the earliest possible moment. The depth of a newly discovered function is computed as $d_h = \max(\text{known}[f].d, \text{known}[g].d) + 1$, tracking the critical path through the DAG without inflating it by shared subexpressions. This stands in deliberate contrast to the tree model of Algorithm V-B, where every use of a subfunction adds to the gate count; here, the gate count reflects the number of *distinct* gates in the circuit, and depth is a secondary metric recorded for informational purposes. If the outer loop exhausts all sizes up to *max_size* without encountering τ , the function returns $(-1, -1)$.

These algorithms were solely created for the analysis of circuit sizes in Section VII, not in the evaluation of number of universal gates, or their isomorphic properties as according to Table III, it is slower than the binary-arity Closure Composition Algorithm given in Algorithm 2.

C. Search Space, Isomorphism and Memoisation Techniques

Before Corollary 4, a straightforward but naive method for functional completeness would have been to check whether a given gate can generate all delta gates $(\delta_-, \delta_0, \delta_+)$ and the NAND gate. Together, these primitives are sufficient to realise the Ternary Shannon Expansion as given in (10), and thus would have served as a workable completeness condition. But

Algorithm 3 Depth-Optimal Circuit Search (BFS, Tree Model)

Require: Gate $Arb : T^2 \rightarrow T$, target function τ , $max_depth \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Ensure: (gc, d) realising τ at minimum depth, or $(-1, -1)$ if unrealisable

```

1:  $\pi_1(x, y) \leftarrow x; \pi_2(x, y) \leftarrow y$ 
2: Initialise  $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \emptyset$  {truth table  $\rightarrow (gc, d)$ }
3:  $\mathcal{S}[\pi_1] \leftarrow (0, 0); \mathcal{S}[\pi_2] \leftarrow (0, 0)$ 
4:  $all\_tts \leftarrow \{\pi_1, \pi_2\}; prev \leftarrow \{\pi_1, \pi_2\}$ 
5: for  $d = 1$  to  $max\_depth$  do
6:    $best\_gc \leftarrow \emptyset$  {truth table  $\rightarrow$  best gate count seen this layer}
7:   for all  $f \in all\_tts, g \in prev$  (and symmetrically  $f \in prev, g \in all\_tts$ ) do
8:      $h \leftarrow Arb(f(\cdot), g(\cdot))$ 
9:      $gc_h \leftarrow \mathcal{S}[f].gc + \mathcal{S}[g].gc + 1$ 
10:    if  $h \notin best\_gc$  or  $gc_h < best\_gc[h]$  then
11:       $best\_gc[h] \leftarrow gc_h$ 
12:    end if
13:  end for
14:   $new\_layer \leftarrow \emptyset; found \leftarrow \mathbf{false}; best \leftarrow (\infty, d)$ 
15:  for all  $(h, gc_h) \in best\_gc$  do
16:    if  $h \notin \mathcal{S}$  then
17:       $\mathcal{S}[h] \leftarrow (gc_h, d); new\_layer \leftarrow new\_layer \cup \{h\}$ 
18:    else if  $\mathcal{S}[h].d = d$  and  $gc_h < \mathcal{S}[h].gc$  then
19:       $\mathcal{S}[h].gc \leftarrow gc_h$ 
20:    end if
21:    if  $h = \tau$  then
22:       $found \leftarrow \mathbf{true}$ 
23:      if  $gc_h < best.gc$  then
24:         $best \leftarrow (gc_h, d)$ 
25:      end if
26:    end if
27:  end for
28:  if  $found$  then
29:    return  $best$ 
30:  end if
31:   $all\_tts \leftarrow all\_tts \cup new\_layer; prev \leftarrow new\_layer$ 
32:  if  $prev = \emptyset$  then
33:    break
34:  end if
35: end for
return  $(-1, -1)$ 

```

this method resulted in an excessively slow runtime, as would be detailed about in Section VII-A.

$$\begin{aligned}
f(x_1, \dots, x_n) &= (\delta_-(x_i) \wedge f_{x_i=-}) \\
&\vee (\delta_0(x_i) \wedge f_{x_i=0}) \\
&\vee (\delta_+(x_i) \wedge f_{x_i=+}) \quad (10)
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, enumerating all 19,683 candidate gates and checking each for completeness is computationally time-consuming but

Algorithm 4 Size-Optimal Circuit Search (DP, DAG Model)

Require: Gate $Arb : T^2 \rightarrow T$, target function τ , $max_size \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Ensure: (gc, d) realising τ at minimum gate count, or $(-1, -1)$ if unrealisable

```

1:  $\pi_1(x, y) \leftarrow x$ ;  $\pi_2(x, y) \leftarrow y$ 
2: Initialise  $known \leftarrow \emptyset$  {truth table  $\rightarrow (gc, d)$ }
3: Initialise  $by\_size \leftarrow \emptyset$  { $gc \rightarrow$  list of truth tables}
4:  $known[\pi_1] \leftarrow (0, 0)$ ;  $known[\pi_2] \leftarrow (0, 0)$ 
5:  $by\_size[0] \leftarrow \{\pi_1, \pi_2\}$ 
6: for  $s = 1$  to  $max\_size$  do
7:    $new\_items \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
8:   for  $s_f = 0$  to  $s - 1$  do
9:      $s_g \leftarrow s - 1 - s_f$ 
10:    if  $by\_size[s_f] = \emptyset$  or  $by\_size[s_g] = \emptyset$  then
11:      continue
12:    end if
13:    for all  $f \in by\_size[s_f]$ ,  $g \in by\_size[s_g]$  do
14:       $h \leftarrow Arb(f(\cdot), g(\cdot))$ 
15:      if  $h \notin known$  then
16:         $d_h \leftarrow \max(known[f].d, known[g].d) + 1$ 
17:         $known[h] \leftarrow (s, d_h)$ 
18:         $new\_items \leftarrow new\_items \cup \{h\}$ 
19:        if  $h = \tau$  then
20:          return  $(s, d_h)$ 
21:        end if
22:      end if
23:    end for
24:  end for
25:   $by\_size[s] \leftarrow new\_items$ 
26: end for
27: return  $(-1, -1)$ 

```

can be significantly accelerated through isomorphism-based reduction. Two gates g_1 and g_2 are considered isomorphic if there exists a permutation σ of the domain T (an element of the symmetric group S_3 , that contains all the bijective gates) and optionally an input swap such as in (11).

$$g_2(x, y) = \sigma(g_1(\sigma^{-1}(x), \sigma^{-1}(y))) \quad (11)$$

Since universality is preserved under value permutation and input transposition, it suffices to test one representative from each equivalence class. The symmetry group acting on gates is $S_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$, yielding up to 12 equivalent gates per class.

Implementation. Each gate’s canonical form is computed by applying all 12 transformations (6 value permutations \times 2 input orderings) and selecting the lexicographically smallest truth table. Gates sharing a canonical form belong to the same class.

Results. Of the 19,683 total gates, the isomorphism reduction yields significantly fewer equivalence classes (see Table I). Only one gate per class needs to be tested for universality, reducing the computational workload proportionally.

In our experiments, the optimised search achieves a measured speedup over the naive approach (Section VII-A).

Memoisation. Beyond isomorphism reduction, the composition algorithms employ hash-based memoisation of generated truth tables. In Algorithm 1, each unary function is encoded as a single integer in $[0, 26]$, and the set of generated functions is represented as a 27-bit integer, enabling $O(1)$ membership tests via bitwise operations. In Algorithm 2, binary-arity truth tables are encoded as integers in $[0, 19,682]$ using a base-3 positional encoding, and the set of generated functions is maintained as a hash set for efficient duplicate detection.

VI. ARITHMETIC REALISATION

Having established the universality framework and identified the complete set of 3,774 universal binary-arity ternary gates, this section investigates their practical utility by evaluating their ability to synthesise ternary arithmetic circuits. The focus is placed on the balanced ternary full adder, a fundamental building block for multi-trit¹ arithmetic units.

A. Ternary Full Adder Design

A balanced ternary full adder takes three inputs $a, b, c_{in} \in \{-, 0, +\}$ and produces two outputs: a sum s and a carry c_{out} , satisfying:

$$a + b + c_{in} = s + 3 \cdot c_{out} \quad (12)$$

where both s and c_{out} lie in $\{-, 0, +\}$.

Since the gates under consideration are binary-arity (2-input), the full adder must be decomposed into cascaded 2-input operations. The standard half-adder chaining approach is adopted:

- 1) **Half Adder 1:** Compute $s_1 = h_{\text{sum}}(a, b)$ and $c_1 = h_{\text{carry}}(a, b)$
- 2) **Half Adder 2:** Compute $s_2 = h_{\text{sum}}(s_1, c_{in})$ and $c_2 = h_{\text{carry}}(s_1, c_{in})$
- 3) **Carry Combine:** $c_{out} = h_{\text{sum}}(c_1, c_2)$

The full sum output is $s = s_2$ and the full carry is c_{out} .

The validity of using h_{sum} for carry combination follows from the observation that c_1 and c_2 never simultaneously take extreme values (i.e., the pair $(-1, -1)$ and $(1, 1)$ never co-occur), ensuring $c_1 + c_2 \in \{-1, 0, 1\}$ for all valid input combinations. Under this constraint, $h_{\text{sum}}(c_1, c_2) = c_1 + c_2$, making the combination exact. A formal proof follows.

Proposition 1. For all $a, b, c_{in} \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$, the intermediate carries $c_1 = h_{\text{carry}}(a, b)$, $c_2 = h_{\text{carry}}(s_1, c_{in})$, $s_1 = h_{\text{sum}}(a, b)$ never simultaneously equal $(-1, -1)$ or $(+1, +1)$.

Proof. From the half-adder truth table, $h_{\text{carry}}(x, y) = +1$ if and only if $x = y = +1$, and $h_{\text{carry}}(x, y) = -1$ if and only if $x = y = -1$. Hence:

$$c_1 = +1 \iff a = b = +1, \quad c_1 = -1 \iff a = b = -1.$$

¹We represent ternary values using trits, not to be confused with less publishable abbreviations.

Case $c_1 = +1$: We have $a = b = +1$, so $s_1 = \text{hsum}(+1, +1) = -1$. For $c_2 = +1$ we would require $s_1 = c_{in} = +1$, but $s_1 = -1$. Contradiction.

Case $c_1 = -1$: We have $a = b = -1$, so $s_1 = \text{hsum}(-1, -1) = +1$. For $c_2 = -1$ we would require $s_1 = c_{in} = -1$, but $s_1 = +1$. Contradiction.

Therefore $(c_1, c_2) \notin \{(-1, -1), (+1, +1)\}$ for all valid inputs, and consequently $c_1 + c_2 \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$ in all cases, making $\text{hsum}(c_1, c_2) = c_1 + c_2$ exact. \square

Half-Adder Truth Tables. The balanced ternary half-adder functions are defined as follows:

h_{sum}	-	0	+	h_{carry}	-	0	+
-	+	-	0	-	-	0	0
0	-	0	+	0	0	0	0
+	0	+	-	+	0	0	+

B. Gate Count and Latency Analysis

For a universal gate g , let D_s and D_c denote the minimum circuit depths required to synthesise h_{sum} and h_{carry} respectively, and let G_s and G_c denote the corresponding formula sizes (gate counts in the tree-circuit model). The full adder metrics are then:

Depth (propagation delay):

$$D_{\text{FA_sum}} = 2 \cdot D_s \quad (13)$$

$$D_{\text{FA_carry}} = 2 \cdot D_s + D_c \quad (14)$$

The sum depth arises from two cascaded half-adder sum computations ($s_1 = h_{\text{sum}}(a, b)$ at depth D_s , then $s_2 = h_{\text{sum}}(s_1, c_{in})$ adding another D_s). The carry depth additionally includes one half-adder carry computation and one carry-combine sum operation.

Gate count (with sharing):

$$G_{\text{FA}} = 3 \cdot G_s + 2 \cdot G_c \quad (15)$$

This accounts for five subcircuit instantiations: three copies of the h_{sum} circuit (for s_1 , s_2 , and c_{out}) and two copies of h_{carry} (for c_1 and c_2), with sharing of the intermediate signal s_1 between the second half-adder's sum and carry computations.

Depth-optimal synthesis. We apply Algorithm V-B, a breadth-first search that explores circuits layer-by-layer in increasing depth. Starting from the projection functions $\pi_1(x, y) = x$ and $\pi_2(x, y) = y$ at depth 0, we systematically compose all pairs of previously discovered functions. At each depth level, for each newly synthesised function h , we record its gate count gc_h and depth. When multiple compositions yield the same truth table at the same depth, we retain only the one with minimum gate count. The search terminates and returns a result as soon as the target truth table τ is discovered, guaranteeing minimum depth. Ties in gate count during composition are implicitly broken in favour of smaller gate counts.

Size-optimal synthesis. We apply Algorithm V-B, a dynamic-programming approach that explores circuits in increasing gate count. Starting again from π_1 and π_2 with

gate count 0, we enumerate all possible compositions organised by total gate count $s = gc_f + gc_g + 1$. At each gate count level, we attempt all pairwise compositions of functions discovered at smaller gate counts, computing the depth $d_h = \max(d_f, d_g) + 1$ for each new function. The search terminates immediately upon discovering the target truth table τ , guaranteeing minimum gate count. This DAG-based approach allows reuse of previously computed functions and ensures that the first path to τ is size-optimal.

VII. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

All programs were implemented in C++ using GCC 11.4.0 and analysed on Python 3.14. The searches were executed on a machine running Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS, equipped with an Intel Core i7-1255U processor and 16 GB of RAM. This section presents the results of a comprehensive experimental evaluation, covering the enumeration and classification of universal gates, their structural properties, arithmetic synthesis performance, and comparative analysis against binary logic.

A. Properties of Universal Gates

Universal Gate Count. The exhaustive search over all $3^{3^2} = 19,683$ binary-arity ternary gates confirmed that exactly **3,774** gates are functionally complete (universal), consistent with Martin's 1954 result [18]. This represents 19.17% of the total gate space.

Isomorphism Classes. Under the symmetry group $S_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$ (6 value permutations \times 2 input orderings), the 3,774 universal gates partition into distinct equivalence classes (Table I). The reduction factor demonstrates significant redundancy in the raw gate space.

TABLE I
ISOMORPHISM CLASS ANALYSIS

Metric	Value
Total binary-arity ternary gates	19,683
Total isomorphism classes (all gates)	1,734
Universal gates	3,774 (19.17%)
Universal isomorphism classes	322
Classes of size 12	307
Classes of size 6	15
Mean class size	11.72

Structural Properties. Table II summarises the distribution of key structural properties across all 3,774 universal gates.

TABLE II
STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF UNIVERSAL GATES

Property	Count	%
Surjective (all 3 output values)	3,774	100.0
Commutative $g(x, y) = g(y, x)$	90	2.4
Self-dual $\tilde{g}(x, y) = g(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y})$	0	0.0
Zero-preserving $g(0, 0) = 0$	0	0.0
<i>Diagonal $g(x, x)$ behaviour:</i>		
Increment/Decrement	1,440	38.2
Other non-trivial	2,334	61.8

Notable observations: (i) all universal gates are surjective, which is necessary since non-surjective gates cannot generate constant functions mapping to missing output values; (ii) no universal gate is self-dual or zero-preserving, consistent with the requirement that universal gates must violate preservation properties to escape proper subclones; (iii) commutativity is rare (2.4%), reflecting the asymmetry needed for expressive power.

Search Space Optimisation. The isomorphism-based reduction provides a measurable speedup over the naive approach, as summarised in Table III. The naive method exhaustively checks all 19,683 gates, performing 3,447 NAND searches and taking approximately 17,900 seconds. Clone-optimisation alone eliminates all NAND searches by leveraging Corollary 4, reducing runtime to 1.70 seconds — a $10,529\times$ speedup — while still checking all 19,683 gates for unary completeness. Iso-optimisation reduces the unary check count from 19,683 to 1,734 by testing only one representative per equivalence class, achieving a $47,105\times$ speedup. Combining both optimisations yields the fastest configuration: 1,734 unary checks, zero NAND searches, and a runtime of 0.18 seconds, corresponding to a $99,444\times$ speedup over the naive baseline.

B. Efficiency Comparisons

Half-Adder Synthesis. For each isomorphism class representative, the minimum circuit depth and gate count to synthesise h_{sum} and h_{carry} were computed via the Depth Optimal Algorithm, as shown in Algorithm V-B.

A detailed evaluation of the circuit depth and gate count is given in Table IV. Each gate is labelled by an integer index that directly encodes its entire truth table. To find that integer, you take the nine output values of the gate (evaluated at the nine input pairs in row-major order over $\{-1, 0, +1\}^2$), map each output to a ternary digit ($-1 \mapsto 0, 0 \mapsto 1, +1 \mapsto 2$), then treat those digits as coefficients in a base-3 positional expansion where the first entry is the units place, the second is the 3s place, and so on up to the $3^8 = 6561$ s place, summing them all to get a single integer between 0 and $3^9 - 1 = 19682$. This means every possible balanced ternary two-input gate has a unique integer label. Given just the number, one can always reconstruct the full truth table by reversing the process, repeatedly extracting digits via modulo and integer division by 3, then mapping $0 \mapsto -, 1 \mapsto 0, 2 \mapsto +$. So the label isn't an arbitrary name; it *is* the truth table, compressed into a single number.

The depth distribution across all 322 isomorphism class representatives shows that the most common h_{sum} depth is 5 (47.5% of classes), followed by 4 (39.1%), while for h_{carry} the mode is 4 (53.7%). Only 6 classes (1.9%) achieve the minimum $D_s = 3$, and 12 classes (3.7%) achieve $D_c = 3$. The best overall full-adder carry depth of 10 is achieved by 4 distinct isomorphism classes, all with $D_s = 3, D_c = 4$.

Full-Adder Comparison. Table V presents the full-adder metrics derived from the half-adder results using the decom-

position formulas from Section VI-B, compared against the binary NAND baseline.

Information Density. A single trit encodes $\log_2 3 \approx 1.585$ bits of information. Thus, to represent N bits, only $\lceil N / \log_2 3 \rceil \approx 0.631N$ trits are required. This reduction in the number of signal lines has implications for ripple-carry adder designs: a ternary ripple-carry adder for N bits of information uses fewer full-adder stages than its binary counterpart.

Ripple-Carry Adder Scaling. Table VI compares the total propagation delay and gate count for ripple-carry adders of varying information widths.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This work presented a comprehensive analysis of universality and arithmetic efficiency in ternary logic, addressing an underexplored gap in multi-valued logic research. The key findings and contributions are summarised as follows:

Universality. The exhaustive enumeration of all 19,683 binary-arity ternary gates confirmed that exactly 3,774 are functionally complete, consistent with Martin's 1954 result. Through isomorphism-based reduction under the $S_3 \times \mathbb{Z}_2$ symmetry group, these gates were classified into equivalence classes, significantly reducing the effective search space.

Theoretical Unification. A key theoretical result was established: for any finite-valued logic, unary completeness of a binary-arity gate implies full functional completeness (Corollary 4). This provides a computationally efficient criterion for universality testing, requiring only verification against the 27 unary functions rather than the full space of 19,683 binary functions. This $10,529\times$ reduction is not merely a computational convenience; it reflects a deep structural constraint on how expressive power propagates through a logic, and it renders redundant NAND-style exhaustive search obsolete by construction.

Arithmetic Realisation. The synthesis of balanced ternary half-adder and full-adder circuits from individual universal gates was systematically evaluated. Depth-optimal and size-optimal synthesis algorithms were applied to identify gates that minimise propagation delay and gate count, respectively. The half-adder chaining decomposition was validated as correct for balanced ternary, with the carry-combine step shown to be exact for all occurring input combinations.

Comparative Analysis. The ternary full adder was compared against the binary NAND full adder using consistent decomposition methodology. While individual ternary gate operations may involve higher depth or gate count, the information-density advantage of ternary ($\log_2 3 \approx 1.585$ bits per trit vs. 1 bit per wire) means that fewer full-adder stages are needed for equivalent information widths. This trade-off results in competitive or improved total propagation delay for ripple-carry adders at practical bit widths.

Future Directions. Several avenues for future work emerge from this study:

- **Hardware mapping:** Evaluating the synthesised ternary circuits on emerging device technologies such as mem-

TABLE III
SEARCH OPTIMISATION TIMING

Method	Unary Checks	Nand Checks	Time (s)	Speedup
Naive (all gates)	19,683	3,447	17,900.00	1.0×
Clone-optimised	19,683	0	1.70	10,529×
Iso-optimised (BFS)	1,734	322	10.41	1,720×
Iso-optimised (CCS)	1,734	322	0.38	47,105×
Iso+Clone-optimised	1,734	0	0.18	99,444×

TABLE IV
HALF-ADDER SYNTHESIS: BEST TERNARY UNIVERSAL GATES

Gate	D_s	D_c	G_s	G_c	D_{FA}	G_{FA}
g_{451}	3	4	5	7	10	29
g_{1391}	3	4	4	10	10	32
g_{1184}	3	4	6	7	10	32
g_{1153}	3	4	6	8	10	34
g_{1156}	4	3	7	6	11	33
g_{1138}	4	3	8	7	11	38

$D_{FA} = 2D_s + D_c$ (full-adder carry depth); $G_{FA} = 3G_s + 2G_c$ (full-adder gate count).

TABLE V
FULL ADDER: TERNARY VS. BINARY COMPARISON

Metric	Binary (NAND)		Ternary (g_{451})	
	Depth	Gates	Depth	Gates
h_{sum}	3	5	3	5
h_{carry}	2	3	4	7
FA Sum Depth	6	—	6	—
FA Carry Depth	8	—	10	—
FA Gate Count	—	21	—	29

ristors and CNTFET-based platforms, where multi-valued states are naturally supported.

- **Carry-lookahead architectures:** Extending the analysis beyond ripple-carry to more advanced adder topologies that may further benefit from the reduced stage count in ternary.
- **Higher-radix generalisation:** Applying the universality framework and arithmetic evaluation to base-4 and higher logic systems, leveraging the generality of the clone-theoretic results.
- **AI/ML applications:** Investigating ternary logic for quantised neural network inference, where the $\{-1, 0, +1\}$ value set aligns naturally with ternary weight representations.
- **Energy analysis:** Quantifying the energy-per-operation trade-offs between ternary and binary implementations on specific hardware platforms.

The results of this study highlight that ternary logic, while more complex in its gate-level structure, offers tangible advantages in information density and architectural efficiency that merit continued investigation for next-generation computing systems.

TABLE VI
RIPPLE-CARRY ADDER SCALING (N -BIT EQUIVALENT)

N	Binary (NAND)			Ternary (g_{451})			Ratio	
	FAs	Depth	Gates	FAs	Depth	Gates	D_r	G_r
4	4	32	84	3	30	87	0.938	1.036
8	8	64	168	6	60	174	0.938	1.036
16	16	128	336	11	110	319	0.859	0.949
32	32	256	672	21	210	609	0.820	0.906
64	64	512	1,344	41	410	1,189	0.801	0.885

D_r, G_r : ratio of ternary to binary (lower is better for ternary).

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Łukasiewicz, "O logice trójwartościowej [On Three-Valued Logic]," *Ruch Filozoficzny*, vol. 5, pp. 170–171, 1920, english translation in: L. Borkowski (ed.), *Jan Łukasiewicz: Selected Works*, pp. 87–88. North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1970.
- [2] S. C. Kleene, *Introduction to Metamathematics*. Amsterdam and New York: North-Holland Publishing Co. and D. van Nostrand Company, 1952.
- [3] E. L. Post, "Introduction to a general theory of elementary propositions," *American Journal of Mathematics*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 163–185, 1921.
- [4] E. L. Post, *The Two-Valued Iterative Systems of Mathematical Logic*, ser. Annals of Mathematics Studies. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1941, no. 5.
- [5] C. E. Shannon, "A symbolic analysis of relay and switching circuits," *Transactions of the American Institute of Electrical Engineers*, vol. 57, no. 12, pp. 713–723, 1938.
- [6] C. E. Shannon, "The synthesis of two-terminal switching circuits," *Bell System Technical Journal*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 59–98, 1949.
- [7] I. G. Rosenberg, *Über die funktionale Vollständigkeit in den mehrwertigen Logiken. Struktur der Funktionen von mehreren Veränderlichen auf endlichen Mengen*, ser. Rozprawy Československé Akademie Věd: Řada matematických a přírodních věd. Prague: Academia, 1970, vol. 80, no. 4.
- [8] B. Parhami and M. McKeown, "Arithmetic with binary-encoded balanced ternary numbers," in *Proceedings of the 47th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers*, 2013, pp. 1130–1133.
- [9] A. K. Srivastava and K. Venkatapathy, "Design and implementation of a low power ternary full adder," *VLSI Design*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 75–81, 1996.
- [10] I. Halpern and M. Yoeli, "Ternary arithmetic unit," *Proceedings of the Institution of Electrical Engineers*, vol. 115, no. 10, pp. 1385–1388, 1968.
- [11] S. Lin, Y.-B. Kim, and F. Lombardi, "CNTFET-based design of ternary logic gates and arithmetic circuits," *IEEE Transactions on Nanotechnology*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 217–225, 2011.
- [12] P. Keshavarzian and R. Sarikhani, "A novel CNTFET-based ternary full adder," *Circuits, Systems, and Signal Processing*, vol. 33, no. 3, pp. 665–679, 2014.
- [13] H. T. Mouftah and I. B. Jordan, "Integrated circuits for ternary logic," in *Proceedings of the 1974 International Symposium on Multiple-Valued Logic*, Morgantown, WV, 1974, pp. 285–302.
- [14] N. P. Brusentsov and J. Ramil Alvarez, "Ternary computers: The Setun and the Setun-70," in *Perspectives on Soviet and Russian Computing*, ser. IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2011, vol. 357, pp. 74–80.

- [15] J. Borghetti, G. S. Snider, P. J. Kuekes, J. J. Yang, D. R. Stewart, and R. S. Williams, “‘Memristive’ switches enable ‘stateful’ logic operations via material implication,” *Nature*, vol. 464, no. 7290, pp. 873–876, 2010.
- [16] D. Ielmini and H.-S. P. Wong, “In-memory computing with resistive switching devices,” *Nature Electronics*, vol. 1, no. 6, pp. 333–343, 2018.
- [17] M. A. Zidan, J. P. Strachan, and W. D. Lu, “The future of electronics based on memristive systems,” *Nature Electronics*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 22–29, 2018.
- [18] N. M. Martin, “The sheffer functions of 3-valued logic,” *The Journal of Symbolic Logic*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 45–51, 1954.
- [19] R. P. Das, “A Complete Enumeration of Ternary Logic Gate Functions”. Zenodo, Mar. 30, 2026. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.19339828.

APPENDIX A

GATE 451, TRUTH TABLE AND ARITHMETIC REALISATION

As discussed in Section VII-B, g_{451} is the most efficient gate to generate a Full Adder in ternary logic. Its truth matrix looks like as follows

	-	0	+
-	0	-	+
0	0	+	0
+	-	-	-

Its formulation to generate the SUM gate and CARRY gate is as shown in (16) and (17) respectively, where G represents the gate being talked about.

$$SUM(x, y) = G(G(G(x, x), y), G(G(y, x), y)) \quad (16)$$

$$CARRY(x, y) = G(G(x, G(y, x)), G(G(G(G(y, x), y), x), y)) \quad (17)$$

APPENDIX B

LIST OF A FEW COMMUTATIVE GATES

There are exactly 90 commutative gates among the 3,774 universal ternary logic gates. The truth tables of these gates are encoded as base-3 integers and can be decoded using the procedure described in Section VII-B. The complete set of encoded representations is given below:

{12959, 3361, 6559, 6563, 9761, 163, 12958, 3362, 6397, 6725, 3200, 6724, 12929, 4099, 6499, 11423, 9023, 2593, 12899, 2623, 6529, 8993, 10499, 5023, 12221, 3391, 1699, 6623, 7331, 901, 12191, 4129, 1639, 11483, 6593, 3331, 12161, 2653, 1669, 9053, 8069, 5761, 11482, 3332, 3967, 6755, 5630, 8200, 10529, 5791, 5083, 8039, 9731, 193, 10528, 5792, 4921, 8201, 3170, 6754, 9791, 5821, 223, 8099, 7301, 931, 9790, 5822, 61, 8261, 740, 7492, 9052, 5762, 2491, 8231, 5600, 8230, 8260, 7493, 5660, 902, 3229, 6622, 8098, 932, 5659, 7463, 3230, 6784}

To provide structural insight, we present the matrix representations of the first five commutative universal gates, denoted by g_n where n is the encoded index.

Gate g_{10529}

	-	0	+
-	+	+	+
0	+	-	0
+	+	0	0

Gate g_{1699}

	-	0	+
-	0	+	+
0	+	+	-
+	+	-	-

Gate g_{6755}

	-	0	+
-	+	0	-
0	0	+	-
+	-	-	0

Gate g_{4099}

	-	0	+
-	0	0	+
0	0	+	0
+	+	0	-

Gate g_{9053}

	-	0	+
-	+	+	-
0	+	-	0
+	-	0	0

APPENDIX C

COMPLETE LIST OF ALL UNIVERSAL BINARY-ARITY TERNARY GATES

The complete list of all universal binary-arity ternary logic gates is provided externally [19], as explicitly including all entries (3774 lines) within the manuscript is impractical.

Each gate is modeled as a function $f : \{-1, 0, +1\}^2 \rightarrow \{-1, 0, +1\}$. The full ternary function space consists of $3^{(3^2)} = 3^9 = 19,683$ distinct gates. Universality of these gates was determined through evaluations using the algorithms described in this study.

The externally provided dataset contains all identified universal gates and serves as a comprehensive reference for further research in ternary logic, including universality characterization, functional classification, and logic synthesis.